

STUDIES IN FRIES MIGRATION. PART V. THE FRIES MIGRATION OF MONOMETHOXYQUINOL ESTERS AND 4-BENZOYLOXY-QUINOL ACETATE

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The Fries migration of monomethoxyquinol acetate and benzoate has been systematically investigated for the first time. The acetate gives 5-methoxyquinacetophenone in small quantity accompanied with a large amount of quinacetophenone, the demethylation taking place during the migration. In case of the benzoate, the migration is complicated; several products—quinol mono- and dibenzoates, monobenzoylquinbenzophenone and benzoic acid, are obtained. It appears that the demethylation first takes place, the course of the migration then being nearly analogous to that of quinol monobenzoate as already described in Part III of this series. 4-Benzoyloxyquinol acetate forms monobenzoylquinacetophenone and quinacetophenone along with quinol dibenzoate and benzoic acid. No diketone could be isolated.

In extension of our work on the Fries migration of quinol esters, described in an earlier part of this series (Part III, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 377), we have now investigated the Fries migration of monomethoxyquinol acetate as well as benzoate.

The perusal of literature shows that the Fries migration of monomethoxyquinol esters has been hardly attempted. Recently, however, Cook, Heilbron and Lewis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 659) found that monomethoxyquinol palmitate and stearate did not migrate under the conditions of the Fries reaction.

The present work on the migration of the acetate (I, R=COMe) was undertaken (i) as a part of the comprehensive study of the migration of quinol esters and (ii) to find whether it can be used as a direct method of preparing difficultly accessible monomethoxyquinacetophenone (II, R=H). It has been found that the migration takes a normal course but the formation of the expected monomethoxyquinacetophenone is not satisfactory, as a good quantity of the product is demethylated to quinacetophenone, the separation being effected by steam-distillation when the monomethoxy derivative is carried over by steam.

The above migration was investigated at different temperatures. To avoid repetitions, the results are summarised in Table I. It is clear from the results that the yield of the monomethoxyquinacetophenone decreases as the temperature at which the migration is carried out is raised.

The isomerisation of the benzoyl ester (I, R=COPh) was found to be interesting. Instead of the expected monomethoxyquinbenzophenone and/or quinbenzophenone by analogy with the acetate, described above, quinol dibenzoate was found to be the main product accompanied with its monobenzoate. It appears that the methoxy group is first eliminated; subsequently the compound behaves as quinol monobenzoate, whose migration has been already described (Part III, *loc. cit.*). The migration was investigated under various conditions, the results being summarised in Table II.

The Fries migration of 4-benzoyloxyquinol acetate (III) was undertaken as it contains two different acid residues viz., acetyl and benzoyl, both being capable of undergoing the migration, and hence interesting products could be expected.

The migration at 98° gave only the traces of quinol mono- and dibenzoates along with the unchanged ester. It appears that the acetyl group is less firmly held than the benzoyl one (cf. Rosenmund and Schnuur, *Annalen* 1923, 461, 56).

At 125°-130° quinacetophenone, traces of quinol dibenzoate, benzoic acid and a colorless product (m.p. 77-78°) were isolated from the reaction mixture. It has been assigned the constitution of monobenzoylquinacetophenone (IV, R = H) as (i) it is soluble in alkali and further, it gives ferric chloride colour test indicating -OH and -COMe groups in *ortho* positions, (ii) on hydrolysis by (conc.) sulphuric acid, it gives quinacetophenone, identified by mixed melting point, and (iii) it gives a benzoyl derivative, identical with quinacetophenone dibenzoate on direct comparison. The migration at 150°-155° gave also the similar results with variation in yields. Thus, at higher temperatures both the groups are affected, since products involving the migration of both the acid residues are obtained.

The above results point out that the acetyl group migrates more easily than the benzoyl one, which is more firmly held to the oxygen atom. It is interesting to note that quinol dibenzoate is also formed as one of the products (cf. Part III).

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

EXPERIMENTAL

Monomethoxyquinol (I, R=H) was prepared according to Robinson and Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 393). The product distilled at 243°-246° solidifying to fibrous needles, m.p. 53-54° (50 g. from 110 g. of quinol).

Monomethoxyquinol acetate (I, R=COMe) was prepared by sodium acetate-acetic anhydride method by heating for 3 hours on a water-bath. On usual treatment with water an oil separated. It was dried and distilled at 235°-236°; the distillate did not solidify even on cooling. It does not give any colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 64.9; H, 6.1. $C_9H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 65.0; H, 6.0 per cent).

Fries Migration of (I).—The acetate (3.3 g., 1 mol.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (8.8 g., 3.3 mols.) were carefully mixed and heated at 60-65° on a water-bath for 1 hour. As the green pasty product obtained by decomposing the reaction mixture by ice and hydrochloric acid (conc., 5 c.c.) could not be satisfactorily crystallised, it was steam-distilled till no oily drops came over. The ether extraction of the distillate gave a green product, which was crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol as small needles, m.p. 50-51° (0.8 g.). It was identified as quinacetophenone monomethyl ether

(II, R=H) by the mixed melting point with an authentic sample prepared according to Kostanecki and Lampe's method (*Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 774).

The residual liquid in the distilling flask on cooling gave a brown product which crystallised from water as greenish needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with quinacetophenone, 201-202° (0.8 g.). A small quantity of a tarry residue was obtained after separation of quinacetophenone.

The *benzoyl derivative* (II, R=COPh) of monomethoxyquinacetophenone was prepared by benzoyl chloride-pyridine method, as colorless silky needles from alcohol, m.p. 61-62°. It is insoluble in sodium hydroxide. (Found: C, 71.1; H, 4.9. C₁₁H₁₀O₄ requires C, 71.1; H, 5.2 per cent).

Other typical experiments carried out with the same amount of reactants, and the period of heating (one hour) are tabulated below.

TABLE I

Expt. No.	Temp.	Solvent.	Quinacetophenone.	5-Methyl ether.
1	95-98°	—	0.8 g.	0.6 g.
2	130°	—	1.2	—
3	60-70°	Nitrobenzene (50 c.c.)	—	—
4	25-30°	(24 hrs.)	—	—

Monomethoxyquinol benzoate (I, R=COPh) was prepared by Schotten-Baumann method as lustrous needles, m.p. 85-86°. It melts to a cloudy liquid which becomes clear at 109°-110°. It appears that it exists in the 'mesomorphic' state between the range 85° and 110° (vide Glasstone, "Physical Chemistry", p. 514).

The Fries migration of this ester was carried out similarly as that of quinol mono- or dibenzoate, already described in Part III. The separation of the different products obtained was also done similarly as before. The results are summarised in the following table.

TABLE II

Monomethoxyquinol benzoate = 3.4 g. (1 mol.). AlCl₃ = 6.6 g. (3.3 mols.).
Reaction period = 1 hour.

Expt. No.	Temp.	Quinol monobenzoate.	Quinol dibenzoate.	Monobenzoyl-quinbenzophenone.
1	95-98°	0.1 g.	0.7 g.	—
2	130-132°	0.5	0.5	0.3 g.
3	150-155°	Traces	0.4	0.3
4	30-35°	—	—	—

Notes: (1) In expt. 1, a trace of benzoic acid and the unchanged ester (0.8 g.) were obtained.

(2) In expt. 4, nitrobenzene (40 c.c.) was used and the reaction mixture left overnight; no crystalline product could be obtained on working up the reaction mixture.

(3) In all experiments, a variable amount of pasty mass was obtained.

4-Benzoyloxyquinol acetate (III) was prepared by sodium acetate-acetic anhydride method from quinol monobenzoate (three hour's heating on a water-bath) as lustrous

leaflets from dilute alcohol (50%), m.p. 124-25°. It gives no colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 70.4; H, 4.8. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 70.3; H, 4.7 per cent). The same compound could be obtained by using a few drops of pyridine instead of sodium acetate.

Fries Migration of (III).—(a). The mixture of the ester (III, 3.8 g., 1 mol.) and aluminium chloride (6.7 g., 3.3 mols.) was heated at 95°-98° on a water bath for 1 hour. On decomposing the reaction mixture as usual, a brown solid was obtained which was dissolved in alcohol for crystallisation; a small insoluble residue remaining over was identified as quinol dibenzoate by mixed melting point. The alcoholic filtrate gave mostly the unchanged ester (3 g.). After its separation, the residual mother-liquor was extracted with dilute sodium hydroxide (2%); on acidification it gave traces of quinol monobenzoate, m.p. and mixed m.p., 162-63°.

(b). The above migration was carried out at 125°-130° for 1 hour, and worked up as before. A trace of quinol dibenzoate was obtained as an alcohol-insoluble residue.

The alcoholic solution gave a product of indefinite melting point (68°-110°), which on extraction with dilute sodium bicarbonate (5%) gave traces of benzoic acid. The residual brown product on extraction with dilute alkali gave a solid which after two crystallisations from alcohol gave colorless needles, m.p. 77-78° (0.5 g.). (Found: C, 70.2; H, 4.8. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 70.3; H, 4.7 per cent). It gives deep yellow colour with alkalis or conc. sulphuric acid and intense red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. It has been identified as monobenzoylquinacetophenone (IV, R=H).

The remaining alcoholic mother-liquor after separation of the above compound was diluted and extracted with hot water repeatedly. The aqueous extract on cooling gave greenish needles of quinacetophenone, m.p. and mixed m.p., 201-202° (0.5 g.).

(c). The reaction was carried out at 150°-155° and the products were separated as in (b). They were benzoic acid (0.3 g.), quinol dibenzoate (0.2 g.), monobenzoylquinacetophenone (0.5 g.) and quinacetophenone (0.3 g.).

In all the above experiments a small amount of uncrystallisable brown residue was always left over after the isolation of the crystalline products.

The hydrolysis of monobenzoylquinacetophenone (0.5 g.) (IV, R=H) by sulphuric acid (conc., 5-7 c.c.) at room temperature for 20-24 hours gave quinacetophenone, identified by the mixed melting point.

The benzoyl derivative (IV, R=-COPh) was prepared by benzoyl chloride-pyridine method as needles from alcohol, m.p. 113-14°. The mixed melting point with an authentic sample, prepared by the benzoylation of quinacetophenone, was undepressed.

The acetyl derivative (IV, R=COMe) was prepared by sodium acetate-acetic anhydride method and crystallised from alcohol as colorless needles, m.p. 76-77°. The mixed melting point with the original ketone was depressed to 58-60°. (Found: C, 68.4; H, 4.9. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 68.4; H, 4.8 per cent).

The semicarbazone was obtained as colorless needles from alcohol, m.p. 245-47° (decomp.).